

PARAMETER SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS IN MULTISCALE AGENT-BASED MODELING OF ATHEROSCLEROTIC PLAQUE PROGRESSION

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Abstract:

Enhancement of precision and reliability in simulation models requires the exploration of advanced sampling techniques and parameter optimization strategies. This study integrates Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) with parameter adjustment methodology to explore the variability of simulation outputs, focusing on an Agent-Based Model (ABM) for atherosclerotic plaque progression sensitive to parameter variations. The ABM model is a multiscale model relying on an input consisting of vessel geometry accompanied with a set of variable and invariable parameters and coefficients. To preserve the integrity of simulations it was of utmost importance to determine a specific range of variables that can be changed without disrupting the simulation as such. The research emphasizes improving model's generalization capabilities by systematically varying parameters within defined ranges, including constant and dynamic parameters, to evaluate their impact on the simulation results.

LHS was used to generate a comprehensive parameter space, consisting of 8 distinct parameters, with two set as constants and the remaining eight subject to variation within specified ranges. The parameters that were considered for LHS were: probability of mitosis, smooth muscle cell (SMC) proliferation in tunica media, parameter driving SMC proliferation in intima, parameter driving mitosis in medial layer, probability of lipid infiltration, probability of extracellular matrix (ECM) degradation, intima thickening coefficient and probability of lipid invading intima. This approach facilitated the generation of diverse, yet evenly distributed, parameter sets to feed into the ABM simulations. The process iteratively adjusted one of the varying parameters to its default value in each simulation run, ensuring a thorough exploration of the parameter space. The simulations were executed based on these parameter sets, and the results were thoroughly analyzed to identify patterns and dependencies.

The application of LHS in conjunction with the parameter adjustment strategy revealed significant insights into the model's sensitivity to various parameters. Initial findings indicate a pronounced impact of certain parameters on the simulation outcomes, specifically the parameter driving SMC proliferation in intima, increased probability of lipid infiltration and increased ECM degradation highlighting their potential as critical levers impacting model's behavior, suggesting areas for further investigation and optimization.

By systematically exploring the parameter space and identifying key parameters with pronounced impacts on model outcomes, this research lays the groundwork for further refinement of simulation practices. Future work will delve deeper into the mechanisms underlying the observed sensitivities and extend the approach to encompass a wider array of models and scenarios.

Keywords: agent-based model, Latin hypercube sampling, parameter optimization, atherosclerosis

Introduction

Finite element modeling of atherosclerosis plays a crucial role in understanding the biomechanical behavior of arterial walls under pathological conditions [1]. Atherosclerosis, a progressive disease characterized by the buildup of plaques within arterial walls, can lead to significant clinical complications such as myocardial infarction and stroke [2]. Computational models based on finite element analysis provide a powerful tool to simulate and analyze the complex mechanical interactions that occur within these diseased arteries [3]. At its core, finite element modeling of atherosclerosis involves discretizing the arterial wall into small geometric elements, each represented by a set of mathematical equations that describe its mechanical behavior [4-7]. These elements are interconnected at nodes, allowing researchers to simulate the distribution of stresses and strains throughout the arterial wall under various physiological conditions. Key factors influencing the mechanical behavior of atherosclerotic plaques include plaque composition (e.g., lipid core, fibrous cap), degree of calcification, and the overall geometry of the vessel [8]. By incorporating these factors into finite element models, researchers can predict stress concentrations within the plaque, assess the risk of plaque rupture, and evaluate the effectiveness of different therapeutic interventions. Moreover, finite element models enable researchers to explore how changes in blood flow patterns, such as those caused by stenosis (narrowing of the artery), influence plaque development and progression [4-7, 9, 10]. By integrating fluid-structure interaction simulations, these models can provide insights into the hemodynamic forces acting on the arterial wall and their role in plaque formation. Recent advancements in computational techniques, coupled with improvements in imaging modalities like MRI and CT angiography, have enhanced the accuracy and predictive capabilities of finite element models in studying atherosclerosis. These models not only contribute to our fundamental understanding of disease mechanisms but also hold promise for personalized medicine by guiding clinicians in making informed decisions regarding patient-specific treatment strategies [11-13].

Given the inherent variability in biological tissues and the complexities of modeling pathological conditions, sensitivity analysis has emerged as a crucial methodology in computational biomechanics [14, 15]. Numerous studies have highlighted the importance of understanding how input parameters affect model outcomes, particularly in finite element models (FEMs) applied to medical and biological systems. Biological tissues, including arteries, exhibit complex, non-linear behaviors that are difficult to capture accurately in computational models due to their anisotropic, heterogeneous, and viscoelastic properties [16]. Furthermore, the variability in material properties such as elasticity, stiffness, and compliance introduces significant uncertainty into FEM simulations, especially when modeling patient-specific cases [4].

In the context of cardiovascular diseases such as peripheral artery disease (PAD), finite element modeling is frequently employed to simulate arterial wall mechanics, blood flow dynamics, and plaque progression [5]. However, the predictive accuracy of these models is often compromised by uncertainties in the input parameters, including plaque composition, arterial geometry, and boundary conditions [6, 13]. This uncertainty is compounded by the pathological changes in the arterial wall caused by plaque accumulation, which alters the mechanical properties of the tissue over time. Therefore, a comprehensive sensitivity analysis is necessary to identify the parameters that most significantly influence model predictions and guide model calibration.

Previous research has demonstrated that sensitivity analysis can reveal critical parameters that drive model behavior, enabling researchers to refine FEMs for improved accuracy. For instance, Suh et al. performed a sensitivity analysis on FEMs of arterial walls and found that parameters such as arterial wall stiffness and pressure significantly influenced the mechanical response of the model [17]. Similarly, in models of atherosclerosis, sensitivity to varying the intrinsic parameters of plaque progression ABM models has been analysed in the paper by Corti et al. where latin hypercube sampling was conducted to generate a variety of parameter combinations, followed by simulations to assess the impact of the varying parameters on simulation outcomes [18].

The insights gained from sensitivity analysis are critical for translating FEMs into clinical practice. Optimized models, calibrated based on sensitivity findings, can contribute to the development of more personalized treatment plans, where individual patient data is used to tailor interventions. The application of FEMs in personalized medicine has gained traction in recent years, particularly in cardiovascular research, where models have been employed to simulate stent deployment, plaque rupture risk, and post-surgical outcomes. Sensitivity analysis, therefore, serves as a foundational step toward achieving these personalized applications by ensuring that FEMs are robust, reliable, and capable of delivering clinically relevant predictions.

In light of these findings, this study applies sensitivity analysis to FEMs that simulate arterial occlusion and plaque progression in PAD. By leveraging a set of patient-specific geometries and parameter variations generated through Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS), we aim to systematically evaluate the impact of various parameters—such as arterial wall stiffness, plaque material properties, and boundary conditions—on the outcomes of the model. Identifying the most sensitive parameters will not only help in improving the accuracy of the FEMs but will also enhance their applicability in clinical decision-making, particularly for predicting disease progression and assessing treatment efficacy.

2. Methodology

2.1. ABM framework

Starting from an initial homeostatic state, the 3D agent-based model (ABM) simulates physiological or pathological arterial wall remodeling, depending on the wall shear stress (WSS) profile, by locally modeling processes such as cell division and apoptosis, extracellular matrix (ECM) production and degradation, and lipid infiltration into the intima. The model operates under the assumption that disease-promoting risk factors are already present. Consequently, plaque formation in a specific area is driven solely by hemodynamic factors, particularly the WSS profile.

The ABM was integrated with an initial Wall Shear Stress (WSS) profile, which induces pathological vascular remodeling by disrupting baseline cellular activity and promoting lipid infiltration and accumulation within the arterial wall. A finite element mesh was created for both fluid and solid domains, with governing equations and numerical methods applied to the fluid domain. Fluid-structure interaction and mesh motion were implemented, with all algorithms incorporated into the PAK - Athero program [19].

At each step, the finite element method (FEM) was used to calculate the velocity distribution, LDL transport, pressure distribution, and shear stress within the lumen area. The ABM utilizes the shear stress and initial LDL distribution from the lumen to begin iterative calculations within the wall for lipid infiltration and accumulation, using a random number generator for each time step. After the ABM iterations, both the lipid distribution and wall geometry are updated, which directly affects the artery's geometry. This geometry, modeled using finite elements that include ABM elements, is then recalculated by running the fluid-structure solver for the lumen domain [13].

A basic solution was developed by carefully adjusting the agent dynamics to stabilize the system near an equilibrium point. This state represents the homeostasis of a healthy artery, which was then disturbed to simulate the formation of atherosclerotic plaque. Before constructing the fully integrated framework, the ABM behavior was tested under both normal and atherogenic conditions.

2.2. Parameter sensitivity analysis

The framework of sensitivity analysis conducted in this paper is presented in figure 1.

Figure 1. Multiparametric sensitivity analysis of PAKAthero ABM

The intrinsic ABM parameters driving the simulation were initially defined by Garbey et al.,[20] and the constant parameters that drive cellular events are:

- Probability of mitosis and apoptosis
- Smooth muscle cell (SMC) division in the intimal layer
- Extracellular matrix (ECM) deposition in intimal layer
- ECM deposition in medial layer
- SMC division in medial layer
- Outward remodeling driven by shear forces
- Outward remodeling driven by tensile forces

All of the aforementioned parameters have been defined in literature and their respective physiological ranges determined (Table 1.).

Table 1. ABM parameters and ranges

Parameter name	Parameter description	Parameter type	Range
α_1	Probability of mitosis and apoptosis	constant	0.05
α_2	Probability of SMC proliferation in tunica media	variable	2-17
α_3	Probability of SMC proliferation in intima	variable	0-0.5
α_4	Probability of ECM degradation	constant	0.008
α_5	Probability of lipid infiltration	variable	0-0.106
α_6	Outward remodeling driven by shear forces	Variable	0-24.46
α_7	Outward remodeling driven by tensile forces	Variable	1.84-100

Multi-parametric sensitivity analysis was conducted using Latin hypercube sampling (LHS) to randomly sample the triangular probability density function of each parameter and define the parameter set for the ABM simulations. This method allowed for the exploratory testing of the entire range of each parameter and is proven to achieve good accuracy with a limited number of simulations. The probability density functions of all parameters were divided into 100 equal probability intervals and an LHS matrix was generated identifying 100 ABM parameter combinations. To account for the influence of these parameters on different initial patient-

specific geometries, 100 simulations with different patient-specific geometries were conducted for 3 distinct cases.

Partial Rank Correlation Coefficient (PRCC) was used as a statistical method to assess the sensitivity of an output variable to changes in multiple input parameters, while controlling for the effects of other inputs. It is particularly useful in sensitivity analysis when inputs are not independent and when relationships between variables may not be strictly linear. PRCC relies on Spearman's rank correlation, measuring the strength and direction of monotonic relationships between ranked variables. By adjusting for the influence of other parameters, PRCC helps isolate the contribution of each input on the model output, making it a robust tool for analyzing complex systems.

Results and Discussion

Figures 2-5 show the PRCCs between the variable model inputs (α_2 , α_3 , α_5 , α_6 and α_7) and target model outputs such as arterial wall, arterial and final content of fibrous plaque type and calcified plaque type respectively.

Figure 2. PRCC for arterial lumen

As it can be seen from Figure 2. α_2 , α_3 , α_5 and α_6 exhibit relatively low but statistically significant PRCC. This implies that the input parameters have a meaningful influence on the output, even if the relationship is not extremely strong. This indicates increasing coefficients of SMC proliferation, lipid infiltration and outward remodeling driven by shear forces leads to a slight but consistent reduction in a physiological outcome, which was expected as all of these parameters should stimulate increased plaque growth thus constricting the arterial lumen.

Figure 2. PRCC for arterial wall

There are no statistically significant PRCC scores for the influence of variable simulation parameters on remodeling of the arterial wall. The arterial wall's response might be driven by a combination of factors working together, rather than any single parameter exerting a dominant influence.

Figure 4. PRCC for fibrous plaque

The only parameter shown to be statistically significant influence on fibrous plaque decrease is the probability of lipid infiltration. From a biological point of view, lipid infiltration leads to plaque progression towards transition to calcified plaque.

Figure 5. PRCC for calcified plaque

Variable parameters α_2 , α_4 , α_5 , α_6 show a statistically significant positive PRCC while α_7 shows a relatively low but statistically significant PRCC. A positive PRCC for α_2 suggests that increased smooth muscle cell activity contributes to plaque growth, while α_4 indicates that weakening of the extracellular matrix exacerbates arterial occlusion. Similarly, α_5 plays a crucial role in plaque formation by increasing lipid accumulation within the artery and α_6 positively affects the lumen, suggesting that hemodynamic forces help maintain or expand the arterial diameter, while α_7 shows a weaker, but still significant, influence on outward remodeling. These findings underscore the complex interplay between cellular proliferation, lipid dynamics, and mechanical forces in the progression of atherosclerosis.

Conclusion

The sensitivity analysis conducted on the ABM provided valuable insights into the model's mechanisms by identifying key influencing parameters, interactions among agent dynamics, and the impact of SMC, ECM, and lipid dynamics on changes in the lumen area. For the arterial wall output, several parameters, including α_2 (SMC proliferation), α_3 (SMC proliferation in the intima), α_5 (lipid infiltration), and α_6 (outward remodeling driven by shear forces), exhibit relatively low but statistically significant PRCCs. This suggests that while these factors influence arterial changes, the relationships are not strongly pronounced. The lack of statistically significant PRCCs for the arterial wall remodeling suggests that its response is likely influenced by multiple factors in combination, rather than any single parameter dominating the process. In contrast, the fibrous plaque output shows that lipid infiltration plays a significant role in plaque progression, transitioning fibrous plaques into more advanced stages, such as calcified plaques. For the calcified plaque output, α_2 , α_4 , α_5 , and α_6 demonstrate a strong positive influence, highlighting the roles of SMC proliferation, ECM degradation, and lipid infiltration in driving plaque calcification, while α_7 also plays a role, albeit with a weaker influence. These findings emphasize the importance of cellular dynamics, lipid infiltration, and mechanical forces in the development and progression of atherosclerosis.

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